

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR DEVELOPING PROJECT SKILLS IN FUTURE TEACHERS

Saidova Nilufar

Shakhrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

Theory and Methodology of Education and Training Primary

Education, 1st year master's student.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15321922>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 29-yanvar 2025 yil

Ma'qullandi: 10-fevral 2025yil

Nashr qilindi: 25-fevral 2025 yil

KEYWORDS

project activities,
educational technologies,
professional competence,
innovative methods, creativity,
problem-based learning,
independent thinking.

ABSTRACT

This article presents the pedagogical foundations of formation and development of project abilities of future teachers and the conditions for their effective organization. The role of project activities in the development of teachers' professional skills, interactive methods, modern educational technologies are analyzed. In addition, effective ways of teaching students to think independently, solve problems and creatively using a project-based approach in the learning process are considered. It also explores the factors of the use of project technology into the teacher training process. It explores the pros and challenges associated with incorporating this approach into the process of building knowledge, skills, and competencies in future teachers. It explores the pros and challenges associated with incorporating this approach into the process of building knowledge, skills, and competencies in future teachers. Through an extensive analysis of the literature and research, this study aims to contribute to the development of effective strategies in preparing future teachers to use project technology in their teaching practice.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the reforms taking place in the education system, the rapid development of modern technologies require the teacher not only deep theoretical knowledge, but also practical skills, creative thinking and a project approach. In particular, project skills play a key role in the professional training of future teachers.

The orientation of the education system to the personal and professional development of future teachers has led to significant changes in the content and technologies of the structure of training specialists in higher pedagogical institutions in recent years. The humanization, differentiation and democratization of pedagogical education make the education system more flexible, diverse and open. As a result, objective conditions have emerged for students to choose educational areas that fully meet their personal and professional needs and aspirations.

Humanization of education is based, first of all, on the idea of education focused on meeting the needs of the student, which was expressed in the transition from literacy pedagogy to person-centered education. The goal of person-centered education is to preserve and form the

mechanisms of self-awareness, self-management, self-development, necessary for the formation of a person's unique personal worldview and dialogical interaction with humanity, nature, culture and civilization. At the same time, by self-awareness we understand the process and result of the maximum development of human inclinations and abilities, their implementation in practical work. This is also the desire of the individual for constant self-improvement.

Self-regulation is a person's constant desire to connect his actions, behaviors, intentions, interests with the interests of other people, their actions and intentions, to motivate himself as a person, without losing his own individuality, to manage the interests of society. . Self-determination is the formation of a person's moral position, affirmation of his "I", awareness of himself, his place in society, his purpose in life. The need to introduce a student-oriented approach in higher education is confirmed by the educational paradigm formed in the process of developing the most important directions of higher education reform.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

It should be noted that the general direction of determining the level of methodological analysis of this problem is research reflecting the philosophical understanding of the essence of preparation for project activities (N. G. Alekseev, Yu. V. Gromyko, VI Zhuravlev, K. M. Kantor, V. V. Kraevsky, V. A. Lek-Torsky, A. M. Novikov, A. V. Rosenberg, VM Rozin, Vn Sadovsky, Vf Sidorenko, vs Shvyrev, G. P. Shchedrovitsky, E. G. Yudin) In a number of publications, normative knowledge for preparation for socio-pedagogical project activities (V. N. Burkov, Ts.J. Jones Garth, A. F., T. Maldonado, Zotov And A. Newell, J. Reitman, G. Simun, P., D. V. Shapiro Tepalik). In some works, the preparation for project activities of a secondary school teacher (O. A. Abdullin, Z. I. Vasilyeva, O. S. Gazman, F. N. Gonobolin, V. Yu. Krichevsky, N. V. Kuzmina, V. A. Slastenin, A. I. Shcherbakov) is considered from the point of view of the preparation of students for project activities. The theoretical and methodological foundations of the developing project paradigm in education were developed to a certain extent in the works of V. N. Averkina, N. V. Bochkina, S. A. Gilmanov, V. I. Zagvyazinsky, V. V. Rubtsova, A. M. Tsyurulnikova, V. A. Sturby, V. Z. Yusupov. They carried out a conceptual analysis and synthesis of theoretical ideas on projecting in various fields of humanitarian knowledge, which allowed them to take a new step forward in understanding the essence of the project paradigm in relation to the goals of reforming and developing Russian education; the general philosophical principle of development was clarified, on the basis of which innovative changes are being implemented in education today; theoretical foundations of preparation for social pedagogical project activities in regional education were developed, defining its essence, general principles, technologies, and methods of project activities in the processes of regionalization of modern education; a general concept was formed. [1; 456,492-b]

RESULTS

Pedagogical design serves as a methodological basis for studying the problems of the quality of professional pedagogical education. "Pedagogical design is a system of coherent, interconnected actions of a teacher aimed at solving pedagogical problems or systematically and consistently implementing a pre-planned pedagogical process in practice." The project problem has its own history, and the term "pedagogical project" is often found in pedagogical literature in the following sense: a project in education is a set of formalized pedagogical ideas aimed at designing an educational system, pedagogical processes and technologies, as well as programs for their practical implementation. In this case, a project, according to E.S. Zaire-Bek, means the development of ideas and programs of activities to transform what is necessary or possible into what is possible. The developed set of ideas and programs of activities (in this study, the individual educational direction of the student) is the product of the project. The

project as a field of professional activity originated in engineering, construction, production, and then spread to activities in the economy, management, social sphere, in particular, to pedagogical activity. According to V.E. Radionova, the multifaceted cultural and historical phenomenon of the project, which is present in all areas of its activity, stems from an important component of the life of any person. Professional pedagogical activity - scientific or practical - is no exception to this line. [3; 68-b]

It has long been proven that any purposeful human activity is associated with planning the possible results of this activity. For centuries, a teacher in everyday practice and education had to make various decisions based only on individual planning of the consequences of such decisions, on his professional intuition developed by previous practical experience.

Project activity forms in students such skills as independent thinking, analysis of problem situations, making creative decisions, and working in a group. By acquiring these skills, future teachers will have the opportunity to work on the basis of innovative approaches in their future pedagogical activities.

It is important to create the following pedagogical conditions for the formation of project skills in future teachers:

- Organizing lessons based on a project approach;
- Using innovative and interactive educational technologies;
- Using tasks aimed at independent and creative activity;
- Introducing project-based methods in pedagogical practice;
- Teaching students the skills of analysis, planning, organization and evaluation.

Modern information and communication technologies create wide opportunities for the effective organization of project activities. For example, group work, project presentations, and remote discussions can be organized through online platforms. [7; 69,86-b]

DISCUSSION

Pedagogical analysis of the development of project skills in future teachers allowed us to make some generalizations:

- Today, when society is undergoing rapid changes and fundamental transformations, preparation for project activities is becoming a fundamentally new and fundamental method of creating conditions for adequate changes in education, identifying internal mechanisms for its development. Preparation for socio-pedagogical project activities as a form of social practice is a specially organized multi-professional activity for the implementation of complex developments in the field of multidisciplinary research and development and educational self-development.

- Preparation for socio-pedagogical project activities is an ideal preparation for project activities (development of the idea of preparation for project activities) and the simultaneous practical implementation of the project plan, related activities (pedagogical, scientific, managerial), a series of integrations - what is possible, or what should be. The integration of this activity is manifested in the preparation for project activities, which are the living carriers of developers and implementers.

-The developing paradigm of preparation for project activities in education, in addition to socio-pedagogical education, also includes the development of educational practice, educational technologies, methods and means of pedagogical activity, and the development of

educational processes that create optimal conditions for the real subject and activity of human life, psychological and pedagogical preparation for project activities. Together, this type of preparation for project activities and the development of new types of educational processes determine the modern image of practically oriented pedagogical science. [7; 69,86-b]

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the development of project skills in future teachers not only increases their professional competence, but also creates the basis for their formation as creative, open to innovation and responsible educators. This, in turn, contributes to an increase in the quality and effectiveness of education. Therefore, pedagogical educational institutions need to establish a well-thought-out educational process in this direction, organized on the basis of modern requirements.

Thus, preparation for project activities in education is an organized system of activities aimed at implementing complex research and project development, ensuring the development of education and self-development as a form of social practice, allowing to meet the needs of a person in education, the needs of the society in which he lives, and the needs of education systems.

The logic of pedagogical project training can be expressed in the following types of activities that change one after another - analysis of current problems or situations, conceptualization, programming, planning and design of new educational practices, as well as forms of organizing the activities of the subjects of the process of training for project activities. In some publications, training for educational project activities is a limited change in the educational system, which allows achieving new goals within the framework of available resources, real funds and a specific organization.

REFERENCES:

1. Дитрих Я. Проектирование и конструирование: Системный подход / Пер. с польск. - М.: Мир, 2001. - 456 с.-с.492
2. Заир-Бек Е.С. Теоретические основы обучения педагогическому проектированию. Дисс. ... доктора пед. наук. - СПб, 1995. - 410 с.-с.40
3. Проектирование педагогических технологий. Учебное пособие. / Сост. Н.Н.Гордеева, В.И.Кривоспицкая. - Екатеринбург: УралГППУ, 2005.-68 с.
4. Муслимов Н. А., Уразова М. Б., Эшпулатов Ш. Н. Касб таълими ўқитувчиларининг касбий компетентлигини шакллантириш технологияси //Тошкент: Fan va texnologiya. – 2013. – Т. 160.
5. Родионов А.С. Структурное моделирование как метод исследования учебно познавательной деятельности школьников (на материалах физики, математики и трудового обучения). Дисс. ...канд. пед. наук. - М., 2007. -180 с.
6. Хилл П. Наука и искусство проектирования. Методы проектирования, научное обоснование решений / Пер. с англ. - М.: Мир, 2003. - 264 с.-с.32
7. Эшпулатов Ш. Н., Пардаева Г. С. Глава 7. Подготовка будущих учителей начальных классов к инновационной деятельности в системе высшего образовательного учреждения //Innovations in education. – 2015. – С. 69-86.

8. Homidov, H. K. "TALABALARNI VATANPARVARLIK RUHIDA TARBIYALASHDA JAMOAT TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATINI MUVOFIQLASHTIRISHNING AMALDAGI HOLATI VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI." Экономика и социум 5-1 (108) (2023): 83-87.
9. Khomidov, Khusniddin Kupaysinovich. "COOPERATION BETWEEN STATE AND PUBLIC ORGANIZATIONS IN THE MEANINGFUL ORGANIZATION OF YOUTH LEISURE ACTIVITIES." Thematics Journal of Social Sciences 7.3 (2021).

